

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

TMEM16A partners with mTOR to influence pathways of cell survival, proliferation and migration in cholangiocarcinoma

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Contains:

Supplemental Fig. S1: Response of Mz-Cha-1 cells to TMEM16A inhibitor.

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Supplemental Fig. S1

A

B

Supplemental Fig. S1. Response of Mz-Cha-1 cells to TMEM16A inhibitor. *A*: Mz-Cha-1 cells, $\sim 1.0 \times 10^3/100 \mu\text{l}$ were plated in 96 well plates and incubated at 37°C overnight. The following day, cells were treated with varying concentrations of T16Ainh-A01 (0-40.0 μM) prepared in DMSO (0.4%). To assess cell survival, 20 μl of MTS reagent was added to all wells on day four, plates were incubated at 37°C for 1 h followed by reading of absorbance at 490 nm. % Cell survival values normalized to the control are shown. Welch's ANOVA test was performed to evaluate difference between control and the treated (**= $P \leq 0.01$). Error bars represent the Standard Deviation. *B*: Mz-Cha-1 cells, $\sim 1.0 \times 10^3/100 \mu\text{l}$ were plated in 96 well plates and incubated at 37°C overnight. The following day, cells were treated with 0, 1.0, 2.0, 5.0 nM of T16Ainh-A01 prepared in DMSO (0.4%). On day 4, cell survival was assessed by addition of 20 μl of MTS reagent, incubation at 37°C for 1 h and reading of absorbance at 490 nm. % Cell survival values normalized to the control are shown. Unpaired t-test with Welch's correction was performed to evaluate the significance between the control and 5.0 nM treatment (**= $P \leq 0.01$). Error bars represent the Standard Deviation.

Supplemental Fig. S2

Supplemental Fig. S2. Response of H69 cells to TMEM16A inhibition. *A*: H69 cells, 1×10^3 were plated in 96 well plates. On the following day cells were treated with T16Ainh-A01 (0, 5, 25 and 75 nM) for 4 days. Morphology was captured with Revolve Inverted Microscope with monochromatic camera (bar=340 μ m). *B*: H69 cells were plated in 6 well plates and grown to confluency. Scratches in the monolayer were made on day 0 and T16Ainh-A01 (0, 50 nM, 200 nM) was applied. The ability of cells to migrate into scratches on day 1 and day 2 was captured with Nikon Inverted microscope. Representative images are shown (bar=100 μ m). *C*: quantitation of cell migration was performed with IMAGEJ software by measuring the distance between the two migrating fronts across the scratch in each condition. The cell migration on Day 0 was set to 1 and normalized % values were obtained for the treatments. Welch's ANOVA test was performed to determine the significance (n.s.= not significant).

Supplemental Fig. S3

Supplemental Fig. S3. Molecular inhibition of TMEM16A in H69 cells. *A*: H69 cells were cultured in 6 well plates and left non-transfected (NT) as control or transfected with nontargeting scrambled (SCR) or mTOR targeting siRNA for 72 h. Cell lysates were prepared and protein was measured with the BCA assay. Equal amount of protein was detected for mTOR, TMEM16A and β -actin. *B*: Equal amount of protein from the above experiment was detected for P-Akt (S473) and Akt in Western blots. *C*: H69 cells, $\sim 5.0 \times 10^4$ were plated in 96 well plates. Following day cells were left non-transfected (NT) as a control or transfected with nontargeting scrambled (SCR) or mTOR targeting siRNA. Cell viability was measured in MTS assay on day 3. Normalized cell survival obtained by setting of the absorbance in the control wells to a 100% is shown. Unpaired t-test with Welch's correction was used to evaluate the significance (n=5, ****= $P \leq 0.0001$).

Supplemental Fig. S4

A

B

Supplemental Fig. S4. Response of Mz-Cha-1 cells to mTORC1 inhibitor rapamycin. *A*: Mz-Cha-1 cells, $\sim 2.0 \times 10^3/100 \mu\text{l}$ were plated in 96 well plates and incubated at 37°C overnight. The following day, cells were treated with varying concentrations of rapamycin (0-0.5 μM). Cells were treated with DMSO alone (0.2%) for control. To assess cell survival, 20 μl of MTS reagent was added to all wells on day 4, plates were incubated at 37°C for 1 h followed by reading of absorbance at 490 nm. % Cell survival values normalized to the control are shown. Welch's ANOVA test was performed to evaluate difference between control and the treated ($n=4$, ****= $P \leq 0.0001$). Error bars represent the Standard Deviation. *B*: Mz-Cha-1 cells were cultured in 6 well plates to 70% confluency. Cells were left untreated as a control or treated with DMSO (0.2%), 0.05, 0.5, 50.0 and 500 nM rapamycin (0.2% DMSO) for 4 days. Cell lysates were prepared and protein was measured with the BCA assay. Equal amount of protein was detected for P-Akt (S473), P-RPS (S235/236) and GAPDH in Western blots.